

Analytical Applications of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea. Part II. Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Silver

R. A. Nadkarni and B. C. Haldar

A rapid spectrophotometric method, based on the yellow colour formed by the reaction of 1-amidino-2-thiourea (ATU) with silver ions in alkaline medium, has been developed for the estimation of trace amounts of silver in the range of 0.4 γ /ml with accuracy of 3.5%. At 400 m μ Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 1-12 γ /ml of the solution. The sensitivity of the method, as defined by Sandell, is 0.03 γ /cm². The effect of diverse ions has been studied. Hg²⁺ and Au³⁺ interfere. This method has been used to determine silver in lead concentrate. The yellow colour appears to be due to colloidal suspension of silver. The reaction leading to colour formation is practically complete at the ratio of AgNO₃: ATU=1:1.

Most commonly used reagents for spectrophotometric determination of silver are *p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine¹ and dithizone². The former is fairly specific for silver. Gold, platinum, palladium, and mercury also react with the reagent. A separation of silver by stannous chloride-tellurium precipitation is necessary to remove interfering ions. The colour is susceptible to change in acidity, reagent concentration, and to a lesser extent on the duration of keeping. Also neutral salts, such as potassium sulphate³ in 1-2% concentration, affect the intensity of the colour. Nitrite produces a deep yellow colour with the reagent and must be removed before the estimation of silver.

In the dithizone method palladium, gold, and mercury interfere and copper is tolerated only when present in moderate amounts. Further, temperature and strong daylight have effect on the intensity of the colour; the reagent dithizone undergoes photodecomposition and oxidation very readily.

Dagnall and West⁴ have described recently the use of Pyrogallol red and Bromopyrogallol red as the spectrophotometric reagents for silver. Both of them are not specific for silver. The amount of EDTA as a masking agent for the interfering cations, e.g., Hg, Al, Zn, Pb, Mg, Ca, and Ba, must be rigidly controlled as even a small excess of EDTA reacts with silver to provide highly erratic results. Moreover, the interference by copper, aluminium, nickel, cobalt, chromium, and halides cannot be prevented. The maximum colour is developed in 2 hr.

Considering the limitations of the above methods, the present authors have investigated spectrophotometric determination of silver with 1-amidino-2-thiourea, used as a gravimetric reagent for silver⁵.

1. Ringbom and Linko, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, **9**, 80.

2. Fischer *et al.*, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1935, **101**, 1.

3. Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959, p. 808.

4. *Talanta*, 1961, **8**, 711.

5. Nadkarni and Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 427.

Spectrophotometric measurements were taken with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, using 1 cm silica absorption cells.

TABLE I
Determination of silver.

S.No.	Silver present.	Silver found by dithizone.	%Error.	Silver found by ATU method.	%Error.
1	200.0 γ	190.0 γ	-0.50	207.00	+3.5
2	200.0	202.5	+1.25	207.00	+3.5
3	100.0	102.0	+2.0	100.00	± 0.0
4	100.0	100.0	± 0.0	100.00	± 0.0
5	50.0	48.0	-4.0	48.75	-2.5
6	50.0	50.0	± 0.0	50.00	± 0.0
7	10.0	10.0	± 0.0	10.20	+2.0
8	10.0	10.0	± 0.0	10.00	± 0.0

Final volume of each solution was 25 ml.

TABLE II
Determination of silver in lead concentrate.

%Ag	Found by the present method	..	0.074	0.072
	Reported in the the certificate	..	0.074	0.074

Composition of the lead concentrate :

Element..	Zn	S	Fe	Pb	Cu	As	Mn	CaF ₂	Bi	Au	Ag
% ..	3.40	14.20	1.35	75.60	0.14	0.32	0.21	0.15	0.02	0.016	0.074

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the absorption curve of silver-amidinothiourea and that of amidinothiourea. Curve C, which is obtained by plotting the difference between the curves A and B, shows a maximum at 360 m μ . All the measurements were taken at 400 m μ because at this wave length absorption due to the reagent was practically absent. Moreover, many coloured cations interfered more seriously at 360 m μ than at 400 m μ .

Conformity to Beer's Law.—It is obvious from Fig. 2 that when the colour is developed in presence of disodium salt of EDTA, Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 1-12 γ of silver per ml of the solution.

Effect of Temperature.—Temperature change in the range of 10-30° has no effect on the colour. Above 30° metallic silver is precipitated. At 10° Beer's law is obeyed even in absence of disodium salt of EDTA.

Effect of pH.—At low pH values the colour development occurs slowly and the colour is less intense than at higher pH. Hence measurements were taken in 0.1 N ammonia solu-

tions which were also 0.1*N* with respect to NaOH. In absence of NaOH, optical density is appreciably low. The minimum concentration of NH_4OH and NaOH required for maximum colour development is 0.05*N*.

FIG. 1 Absorption spectra for silver-ATU system.
Curve A—5 γ/ml . Ag+ATU.
Curve B—ATU blank
Curve C—Diff. in O.D. of A and B.

different from the calibration graph prepared in their absence. So the colour in the solution of known and unknown concentrations must be developed under identical conditions. The limiting concentrations of Cr^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , and Co^{2+} , which can be tolerated in the determination of silver, are 26.0, 19.2, and 23.56 γ/ml respectively. Pd^{2+} is complexed as soluble dimethylglyoximate in ammoniacal solution. Hg^{2+} and Au^{3+} interfere. The following anions do not interfere: F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SO_3^{2-} , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} , CNS^- , PO_4^{3-} , $\text{P}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$, $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$, CO_3^{2-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , WO_4^{2-} , MoO_4^{2-} , VO_3^- , AsO_4^{3-} , AsO_3^{2-} , acetate, citrate, tartrate, selenite, and tellurite.

Effect of Time.—The colour development is instantaneous and the stability of the colour depends on the concentration of silver. In the range 1-6 γ/ml of silver, the colour is stable for at least 6 hr., whereas in the range 7-15 γ/ml , the colour fades after $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Daylight has no appreciable effect on the intensity of the colour. Above 15 γ/ml of silver, optical density of the solution rapidly decreases due to precipitation of metallic silver.

Effect of Diverse Ions.—Under the experimental conditions employed, the interference by Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Bi^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Th^{4+} , Ce^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Mn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Sn^{2+} , and V^{4+} ions is absent. Sodium tartrate suppresses the interference due to Fe^{3+} and Sb^{3+} . Sodium citrate is used to mask UO_2^{2+} and Cr^{3+} . Calibration graphs, prepared with solutions containing sodium tartrate and sodium citrate, are, however,

FIG. 2 Calibration curve for silver-ATU.
 $\text{pH}=13$. Wave length=400 $\text{m}\mu$.

Cyanide interferes at all pHs. It forms complex with silver so strongly that no colour is produced with the reagent. This interference can, however, be prevented by using formaldehyde.

It may be concluded from the results recorded in Table I that amidinothiourea method compares very well with the dithizone method. Silver as low as 0.4 γ /ml of solution can be estimated by amidinothiourea method with an accuracy of 3.5%. The sensitivity of the reaction, as defined by Sandell¹², is 0.03 γ /cm². The molar absorption index of the coloured product at 400 m μ is 3240 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Stoichiometry of the Reaction and Nature of the coloured Product.—The reaction between silver and 1-amidino-2-thiourea has been studied by Job's continued variation method¹³ and by mole-ratio method¹⁴. The results of both the methods indicate that silver and 1-amidino-2-thiourea react in the ratio of 1:1. In the mole-ratio method the maximum colour (Fig. 4) is observed at the point corresponding to Ag: ATU = 1:1 and further increase in the concentration of ATU does not cause any increase in the intensity of the colour. It is therefore concluded that the reaction between silver ion and ATU is practically complete at the point 1:1.

Volume of silver nitrate solution in ml.
 FIG. 3. Job's continued variation method.
 Curve A—0.00032 M-AgNO₃ and ATU.
 Curve B—0.0005 M-AgNO₃ and ATU.
 Curve C—0.001 M-AgNO₃ and ATU.
 pH=13. Wave length=400 m μ .

Concentration of ATU in moles.
 FIG. 4. Mole-ratio method.
 Curve A—10ml 0.001 M AgNO₃+10ml ATU.
 Curve B—5ml 0.001 M AgNO₃+5ml ATU.
 pH=13.—Wave length=400m μ .

On centrifuging, the coloured solution becomes colorless and brown solids settle at the bottom of the centrifuge cone. Further, the yellow colour can be removed by filtering the solution through a sintered-bed crucible. These observations suggest that the yellow colour is due to colloidal suspension of silver. This is also supported by the deposition of metallic silver from coloured solution kept beyond certain time. It is, however, interesting

12. "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1959, p. 83.
13. *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.
14. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

to note that large amounts of neutral salts, such as NaNO_3 , Na_2SO_4 , and NaCl , have practically no effect on the colour.

Determination of Silver in Lead Concentrate.—The alloy (400 mg.) was dissolved in minimum quantity of nitric acid and the solution was filtered to remove the insoluble matter. The colour was developed in presence of sodium tartrate and disodium salt of EDTA by following the procedure described above. Absorbance was measured at 400 m μ . Correction for presence of gold was applied. The results shown in Table II are in good agreement with the value for silver reported in the certificate of Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., Yorks, England.

The main advantage of the present method over other known methods is its freedom from the rigid control of acidity, indifference to the effect of neutral salts and strong daylight, and the noninterference by anions and EDTA.

One of the authors (R.A.N.) thanks the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for the award of a research training scholarship during the tenure of which this work has been carried out. Their thanks are also due to Dr. D. V. Ball, Director, Institute of Science, for allowing them to use the spectrophotometer of the Zoology Department, and to Dr. J. S. Dave of M.S. University of Baroda for supplying the lead concentrate sample.

INORGANIC AND NUCLEAR CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY-1.

Received July 11, 1963.